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**INCLUSIVE PERFORMING ARTS
WITHIN UKRAINIAN CULTURAL
FOUNDATION WORK**

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The purpose of the article is to comprehend the importance of the Ukrainian Cultural Foundation (UCF) (2017-2019) to develop inclusive performing arts in Ukraine analytically. The research methodology provides generalisation and analysis of the activities of the UCF on the policy of providing grant support and forecasting trends in the development of domestic inclusive performing arts. Scientific novelty. According to the UCF work results, the authors studied the structure of grant support for projects, traced the activity evolution and analysed inclusive performance features. Conclusions. In Ukraine, despite the socio-economic shocks, the state pays attention to the development of cultural and artistic practices, including inclusive ones. An important place in this process is occupied by Ukrainian Cultural Foundation, which provides funding for different cultural and artistic projects on a competitive basis. Foreign partners provide donor support. In 2019, a significant share of a grant under the Inclusive Arts programme received the Performing Arts sector, and many productions were funded. The article states the facts as follows: UCF supports projects throughout Ukraine but annexed Crimea and temporarily occupied territories of Donbas with some dominance of Kyiv; amateur groups' stage productions received vast majority of grants; inclusive stage projects were not limited to the creation of theatrical performances and their public performance, but were accompanied by public rehabilitation and educational activities. The author drew attention to the fact that there is none that would help solve people's problems with dwarfism among the projects.

Keywords: Ukrainian Cultural Foundation; inclusive performing arts

Introduction

Among the members of any society are citizens with disabilities. "According to the official data of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, as of January 1, 2019, the number of people with disabilities was 2659.7 thousand or 6.3% of the total population" (Yakushenko, 2019, p. 3). However, due to the steady growth of the proportion of inhabitants with special needs in the country's population structure, the issue of their social protection in Ukraine is very acute. According to the National Institute for Strategic Studies, the dynamics of the total number of people with disabilities in Ukraine at the beginning of 2001–2019 can be traced as follows: 2001 — 2 597.5 thousand people; 2006 — 2 495.2 thousand people; 2011 — 2710.0 thousand people; 2015 — 2 568.5 thousand people; 2017 — 2 603.3 thousand people; 2018 — 2 635.6 thousand people and in 2019 — 2 659.7 thousand people (Yakushenko, 2019, pp. 3-4). The growth of statistical indicators is due to Ukrainian society's socio-economic development: declining living standards, health care, safety and job security, environmental culture, the growing number of various cataclysms — human-made, natural, ecological and military.

Recent research and publications analysis. In recent decades, there has been a positive trend in the world towards people with disabilities. There is a transition from charity to respect for the rights of people with disabilities. The institutional duty of the state and society was to create a holistic system based on modern principles of ensuring adequate social protection and support, social integration, creating equal opportunities for self-realisation, full life, education and employment, the inclusion of people with disabilities in spiritual, cultural and sports life. Over the last decade, Ukraine has increasingly paid attention to the problems of inclusion in society. Evidence of this, for example, are two Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of August 21, 2019, No. 779 "On the organisation of inclusive education in out-of-school education" (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2019a) and No. 530 of April 10, 2019 "On approval of the Procedure for organising inclusive groups in preschool education institutions" (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2019b), which regulate, respectively, the order of organisation of inclusive education in out-of-school education institutions and

preschool education institutions. Ukraine has acceded to international law, ratified the International Labour Organization conventions, and reoriented the state's policy on persons with disabilities following recognised standards observed in highly developed civilised countries.

The Ukrainian Cultural Foundation is one of the few organisations in Ukraine that is entangled in inclusive arts. M. Chorna (2020), based on illustrative examples from the list of 2018-2019 UCF competitive programmes, conducted an analytical study on the role of inclusion in the culture of Ukraine. Journalist K. Marquardt (2018) talks about inclusion in art as a component of the Goethe-Institut, namely, in the field of music and fine arts, tourism services and museum activities. In December 2020, a public discussion on “Inclusion — Publicity — Culture” took place in Lviv, where during the round table, a wide range of specialists as theatre critics, journalists, art managers of inclusive activities discussed the role of people with disabilities in art. (Lvivian Zaproshuii Podyskutuvaty, 2020). M. Yudov and K. Pyvovarova researched some aspects of inclusive theatrical, educational activity in Ukraine, in particular the professional training of drama theatre actors. Based on their own experience of working with students with special educational needs, in particular with Down's syndrome, the authors outlined a range of pressing issues in the system of inclusive arts education in Ukraine (Yudov & Pyvovarova, 2018).

Purpose of the article

The article aims to analytically comprehend the importance of the Ukrainian Cultural Foundation to develop inclusive performing arts in Ukraine.

Main research material

Ukrainian Cultural Foundation results

Today, the attitude to people with disabilities is gradually changing in the public consciousness, the topic of inclusion is beginning to occupy an increasingly important place in public opinion. Cultural and artistic practices are often a tool for solving inclusion problems.

One of the few state institutions in Ukraine that systematically supports cultural and artistic projects, including inclusive, is the Ukrainian Cultural Foundation (UCF) — a newly established state institution in 2017, which activities are aimed at providing financial support and promotion of initiatives on a competitive basis in the field of culture and creative industries. The UCF work is an integral part of state policy, which, in turn, is determined by the priorities of the Ministry of Culture of Ukraine.

By the strategic goals of the UCF to promote the creation of a cultural product, strengthen the role of culture in society, internationalise Ukrainian culture and increase its institutional and financial capacity, its activities are aimed at the following areas of cultural and artistic creativity: audiovisual art; visual arts; audio art; performing arts; design and fashion; literature and publishing; cultural heritage; cultural and creative industries.

In 2019, with the assistance of the UCF, 432 cultural and artistic projects were implemented. Among them: 1 VR-film, 4 analytical studies; 3 audio guides, 4 audio recordings, 47 different types and thematic directions of publications; 27 performances, 24 exhibitions, 1 tour, 1 expedition, 40 film productions, 3 competitions, 7 conferences, 4 concerts, 3 mobile applications, 3 mobile applications with AR, 3 board games, 18 online resources, 58 educational programmes, 1 fashion show, 1 award, 13 pre-productions, 4 animation productions, 7 promotional companies, 20 residences, 55 scripts, 14 TV productions, 4 participations in international network events, 59 festivals, 3 hubs.

17% of applicants (74) recipients of grants in 2019 have already cooperated with the UCF in 2018. In 2019, 75% of the winning projects were submitted by private organisations and only 25% — by public (<https://ucf.in.ua/en/>).

Every year UCF expands its activities. Thus, the budget of competitive programmes in 2018 amounted to 156.66 million UAH¹, and in 2019 — 641 million UAH², the demand for grants increased accordingly from 333.71 million UAH. up to UAH 2 970.13 million, the actual amount of grants from UAH 139.42 million up

¹ According to the Ministry of Finance, the average exchange rate of hryvnia to the USA dollar in 2018 was UAH 27.2 to one USA dollar.

² According to the Ministry of Finance, the average exchange rate of hryvnia to the USA dollar in 2019 was UAH 25.8 to one USA dollar.

to 497, 87 million. The number of submitted applications in 2018 — 716, in 2019 — 2 059, in 2020 — 2 373. Implemented projects in 2018 — 293, in 2019 — 432. The number of experts involved has increased: in 2018, there were only 60, in 2019 — 158, and in 2020 — already 509 people.

From year to year, the UCF remains true to its strategic goals, although it periodically changes its approach to the formation of competitive programmes to some extent. For example, in 2020, the UCF is not supporting any applications where production is considered the project's main product. In 2020, the UCF announced the following 10 competitive programmes for applications with the subsequent budgets for funding: Cultural Analytics (aims to compensate for the lack of knowledge about cultural sectors, lay the foundation for the systematic study of markets, audiences and social transformation in culture (UAH 20 million³)); Innovative cultural product (designed to develop various sectors of culture through an innovative approach (UAH 102 million)); Audiovisual Arts (aimed at supporting and developing the Ukrainian audiovisual sector, the latest multimedia technologies, Ukrainian television and radio broadcasting (UAH 70 million)); Networks and audiences (designed to promote the formation of sectoral and intersectoral networks in the cultural and artistic sphere (UAH 20 million)); Culture. Tourism. Regions (designed to enhance the tourist attractiveness of regions by stimulating local cultural development of communities (UAH 10 million)); Training, Exchanges, Residences and Debuts (aimed at developing the exchange of knowledge, experience and ideas in the field of culture and arts, as well as the discovery of new artistic practices and names (UAH 60 million)); Prominent events for Ukrainian culture (aimed at support for cultural diversity and increasing the role of culture in the life of Ukrainian society (UAH 100 million)); Cultural Capitals of Ukraine (enables Ukrainian territorial communities to claim the status of a European Capital of Culture (UAH 40 million)); Culture for Change (aimed at supporting young artists, organisations and cultural operators seeking to establish new cultural ties between Ukraine and Germany (UAH 10 million)) and the Inclusive Arts programme aimed at attracting the potential of artists with disabilities to cultural and artistic life in the country (30 million UAH) (<https://candoco.co.uk/>).

Thus, it can be argued that in Ukraine since 2017, as part of the multi-vector activities of the Ukrainian Cultural Foundation at the national level, the programme for the development of inclusive arts is funded and operational.

Inclusive arts is one of the priorities of the UCF activity

The Ukrainian Cultural Foundation pays special attention to the problems of inclusion in Ukrainian society. Within the Foundation's programmes, inclusion is seen as "a process of increasing opportunities for the participation of all citizens in social life and cultural activities. This process involves recognising and overcoming barriers and building a comfortable society with equal opportunities for all citizens, regardless of their physical or psychological characteristics" (Ukrainian Cultural Foundation, 2019).

The UCF Inclusive Arts Support Programme has been developed in collaboration with the British Council in Ukraine as part of Unlimited's international art programme: Making the Right Moves. "Since its inception in 2015 as a programme of the British Council, it has had a significant impact on the arts and theatre, as well as on the lives of people with disabilities" (Ukrinform, 2019). One of the iconic partners of Unlimited: Making the Right Moves is the Candoco Dance Company, which creates choreographic performances by professional dancers with and without disabilities (British Council Ukraine, n.d.).

The vast majority of UCF competition programmes contain several lots⁴. For example, the Inclusive Art programme has three ones: 1) "Supporting artists with disabilities", the purpose of which is stated in the title of the lot and involves participation in projects of artists with disabilities both as authors and as participants; 2) "Inclusive cultural product", which provides for the creation of a cultural and artistic product adapted for access of people with disabilities or is a method of their social adaptation; 3) "Inclusive Society", which is designed to foster respect for the rights of people with disabilities through emphasis in cultural and artistic products on inclusion, as well as promoting the work of artists with disabilities and training to work with inclusive audiences in creating educational and artistic projects. The first lot provides for a budget of UAH 15 million with a minimum grant amount of UAH 100,000 and a maximum of UAH 1 million. The budget of the second lot includes expenses for UAH 10 million and stipulates grants from UAH 100,000 to UAH 500,000. Finally, in the third — UAH 5 million with the same restriction on the size of grants (Ukrainian Cultural Foundation, 2020).

The list of applications for grants from the Foundation for the creation of cultural and artistic products under the Inclusive Arts programme includes the following items: festivals and events, cultural and creative

³ The State budget of Ukraine for 2020 is based on the exchange rate of UAH 27.5 to one USA dollar.

⁴ Lot — the amount of material that is considered as one set for sampling.

spaces, inclusive residences; publishing of books, periodicals, magazines, print media, literary festivals; creation of works on painting, graphics, mosaics and installations; works of life and reproduced music, sound art, radio; musical and theatrical performances, performances, events. The list proposed by the Foundation is not exhaustive.

In 2019, the UCF Inclusive Arts programme in cooperation with the British Council in Ukraine under the art programme Unlimited Making the Right Moves art programme financed 39 projects including 13 performances, 7 publications, 7 educational programmes, 4 exhibitions, 2 audio recordings, 2 online resources, 2 festivals, 1 audio guide, 1 hub (<https://ucf.in.ua/en/>). It is worth noting that among the created performances were a puppet, musical and dramatic, translated into sign language, as well as dancing with the participation of performers in wheelchairs and those with mental disabilities, adapted for viewers with epilepsy, autism and Down's syndrome.

By support sectors, grant aid under the Inclusive Arts programme was distributed as follows:

- performing arts UAH 6,174,101.90
- literature and publishing UAH 2,389,842.13
- cultural heritage UAH 1,846,648.92
- cultural and creative industries UAH 2,108,641.29
- visual arts UAH 1,364,724.83
- audio arts UAH 956 780.00

In the Performing arts sector, 14 individual projects and 1 national cooperation were financed and implemented (<https://ucf.in.ua/en/>).

The projects supported by the Foundation provided people with disabilities with the opportunity to learn cultural and artistic practices to earn an income and help to reduce their discrimination in the labour market. At the same time, the vast majority of projects supported by this programme are sustainable. In particular, the performances created in cooperation with permanent theatres continued to exist and found their place in their repertoires. In addition, printed comics, books, and audio guides and digital resources are freely available on the Internet.

Inclusive performances supported by Ukrainian Cultural Foundation in 2019.

Let's consider the projects implemented by UCF in 2019 in the form of performances under the Inclusive Arts programme in the field of cultural and creative industries related to the performing arts:

1. In the framework of the Space of Opportunities social and artistic project by Poltava Academic Regional Puppet Theatre (Poltava) in partnership with the Kharkiv Theatre Centre Charitable Foundation (Kharkiv), created an interactive multi-sensory play "On the Wave". In addition, the project equipped a Space of Opportunities theatre sensory hall as an additional means of socialisation and social adaptation of children with special needs. Furthermore, a Theatre and Inclusion seminar training was held with actors, directors, playwrights, scenographers and theatre critics, and psychologists, correctional teachers and rehabilitation specialists. The project brought together leading Ukrainian specialists from Dnipro, Kyiv, Lutsk, Poltava, Ternopil, Kharkiv, Khmelnytsky and Chernivtsi.

2. The View inclusive, multidisciplinary eco-performance. As part of the project, the Academy of Ukrainian Youth Public Youth Association (Lviv) hosted a The View inclusive, multidisciplinary eco-performance, which involved young professional artists and visually impaired people. The idea of the performance was to offer the viewer a view of everyday reality that people deprived of visual perception have, compared to people focused on the visible channel of the worldview. The project also covered environmental issues and became a place for implementing artistic innovations (upcycling) to produce scenography and scenery.

3. Varash City Centre for Comprehensive Rehabilitation for Persons with Disabilities named after Z. A. Matvienko (Rivne region, Varash), implemented the Impress and Inspire project. During its implementation, an educational campaign was created, and many artistic events were held, which were attended by creative children and adolescents, including those with disabilities, who by their example demonstrated success in art and inspired others. The project consisted of theatrical performances, an exhibition of photographs and other works of art by artists with disabilities, amateur actors and city residents. The project also created an educational video on equality of rights and overcoming stereotypes.

4. The White Cube: Theatre Beyond Sounds project was implemented by the "We Are Together" Centre for Civil Initiatives public association (Kyiv). A Pinocchio children's puppet show was created within the project framework, where children and adolescents with and without disabilities performed all roles. During the performance, it was translated into sign language. With the financial support of the Ukrainian Cultural Foundation, the authors of the project were able to significantly help deaf and hard of hearing children in Ukraine to

overcome restrictions on the exercise of their cultural rights through information isolation, language barriers, and social stereotypes about people with disabilities. The White Cube: Theatre Beyond Sounds project aimed to build a bridge of trust and friendship between deaf and hearing children through creativity.

5. Hear the World inclusive theatre (Kyiv) presented a play based on Lana Ra's *Witch-Monsters*, which was staged by 15 children aged 8-11 from different regions of Ukraine — Kyiv, Zhytomyr, Cherkasy, Dnipro, Kharkiv — (7 children with hearing impairments and 8 — without it) in a children's camp near Kyiv. Professional theatre directors, actors, animators, and professional art therapists helped the children during the project gain a unique experience of self-development, integration into society, and tolerance. The play was presented at the Kyiv Academic Theatre for Young Spectators and toured the regions of Ukraine, drawing public attention to the problems of people with hearing impairments and promoting the ideas of inclusion. The implementer of the Let's Grow Healthy project Public Association (Yakushenko, 2019).

6. "Not special, but a person!" project embodied by the Mykolaiv Academic Regional Puppet Theatre (Mykolaiv). It included the production and screenings of a *Mowgli* inclusive puppet show. The winged phrase from the famous work of R. Kipling, "We are of one blood, you and I", became the main slogan of the project, aimed at involving deaf people actively in cultural and artistic life and fostering a tolerant attitude towards society. Working on the play, its authors combined the means of expression of puppet theatre, plasticity and sign language, making it accessible to all categories of spectators. The project also included joint adaptation and entertainment activities for people with disabilities, project participants and spectators.

7. Under the Jewish-Ukrainian Social Initiative Charitable Foundation (Kyiv) initiative, an inclusive cultural and artistic intervention, Chain Reaction of Inspiration, was created. The result of the project was the Chain Reaction of Inspiration performance, which provided artists with disabilities with equal opportunities to participate in the modern cultural life of the country. Furthermore, the project introduced an inclusive model of mutual artistic therapy of people with mental and other forms of disability and representatives of the wider Ukrainian society. The project consists of a series of stage and performance events created jointly by inclusive arts centres in Kyiv, Lviv, and Odesa. As part of such events, creative teams of people with disabilities were able to release individual creative potential and create a joint theatrical programme involving guests in the co-creation of the event.

8. Zaporizhzhia Charitable Foundation Jewish Community Centre Mazal Tov (Zaporizhzhia) initiated a "Creativity without restrictions" inclusive marathon. There were screenings of the *Light in the Dark* theatrical play, a *Strong in Spirit* photo exhibition and a gallery of creative works was opened. The *Equal Opportunities* theatre troupe created the *Light in the Dark drama*. Various training events for artists with disabilities also took place over three months. The main goal of the project activities was to overcome stereotypes and encourage public interest in works of inclusive arts through the implementation and presentation of socio-artistic initiatives.

9. The Public Association, "Dzherela Charitable Society for Assistance to Persons with Disabilities as a Result of Intellectual Disabilities" (Kyiv), staged "Is There a Right?" socially interactive play. In general, within the "Is there a right?" project. There were productions and screenings of an interactive play performed by amateur actors with disabilities due to intellectual disabilities, members of the social-interactive theatre of the Sources Charitable Society. The play is based on the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and the participants' own stories. Also, during the project, methodical recommendations on creating an interactive performance with the participation of people with disabilities due to intellectual infringements were developed.

10. Under the auspices of the Department of Culture, Nationalities and Religions of the Vyshhorod District State Administration (Kyiv oblast, Vyshhorod), *Lullaby for the Dragon* performance by the Perfeco in Kilaba children's inclusive theatre was staged. The authors worked on the play script directly with its participants, creating a therapeutic effect of art. The central theme of the production was internal fears, thoughts, prejudices and their impact on people's self-awareness. The project also included sessions involving tutors from the regional resource centre and leading actors from the MonoFon theatre to explore the play's theme and develop the participants' artistic potential.

11. The Theatre of Special People project was created under the auspices of the Ivano-Frankivsk City Centre for Social and Psychological Rehabilitation of Children and Youth with Functional Disabilities "Dyvosvit" (Ivano-Frankivsk) to socialise and integrate people with special needs into society, forming special centre theatres in Ivano-Frankivsk. Yulia Kushnir's *Green Lips*, 24 play about neighbours' lives on one of the cosy streets was staged as part of the project. But what made it special was not the plot line, but young actors-performers with intellectual disabilities, who had the opportunity to work on pronunciation, acting skills, or memory and

gained experience working with a professional, experienced director, actor Drama Theatre Eugene Kholodnyak. In addition to the play's premiere, the project also included master classes and training events for project participants and performers.

12. The Platform of Theatre Initiatives NGO (Kharkiv) within the project staged a *Three Foxes* inclusive play for children — a musical play for children 3-9 years, based on folk tales about the inhabitants of the forest — foxes, cats, crows and a lion. The creative team actively cooperated with specialists in child psychology, rehabilitation, and inclusion throughout the project and conducted training and workshops. Performances took place in Kharkiv and Poltava.

13. Within the 2019 Inclusion in Harmony project of the All-Ukrainian Association Development NGO (Vinnytsia) created a dance performance with artists with and without disabilities from different Ukrainian cities. The play is dedicated to eternal themes — love, friendship, love for the country, willpower. It declares that there should be no barriers between people, and the Good should always prevail. The project aims to integrate people with disabilities into the cultural and artistic environment. Performances took place in the cities of Khmelnytskyi and Rivne. It was attended by more than a thousand spectators, as well as more than 300 thousand people watched a video of the play on the Internet.

Conclusions

Despite current socio-economic upheavals, Ukrainian society pays attention to the development of cultural and artistic spheres of activity. In particular, in 2017, the Ukrainian Cultural Foundation started operating in the country, which provides funding for cultural projects of various vectors on a competitive basis. As a result, the UCF activity is rapidly developing and constantly improving.

In addition to the state, the project donors are foreign partners. In particular, the programme to support inclusive arts was created with the participation of the British Council in Ukraine and operated within the framework of the international art programme Unlimited: Making the Right Moves.

In 2019, Leading support for grant assistance under the Inclusive Arts programme the Performing Arts sector received, where, in turn, the number of funded projects (39 in total) was dominated by performances (13). Analysing the projects supported by the Foundation, it can be stated that:

- the geography of the projects actually covers the entire territory of the country except for annexed Crimea and the temporarily occupied territories of Donbas with some dominance of Kyiv (4 out of 13 performances);
- the lion's share (11) consisted of stage productions created only by amateur groups;
- inclusive stage projects were not limited to the creation of theatrical performances and their public showing but were accompanied by public rehabilitation and educational and popular events.

Furthermore, in our opinion, with all the variety of inclusive artistic practices presented for consideration and supported by the Ukrainian Cultural Foundation, it is noteworthy that they are not presenting the problems of life of people with dwarfism. The creative path of the famous theatre and film actor Peter Hayden Dinklage and his role as Tyrion Lannister in the *Game of Thrones* drama television series (2011) is a confirmation of the thesis that people with atypically short stature, having equal rights with other members of society, can be well represented in the field of stage practices, film and television industry. Two students with disabilities are already studying Performing Arts at the Kyiv University of Culture: a director of pop and mass holidays student and an actor of theatre and cinema student. Both students and their groupmates together are training the chosen speciality. It should be noted that today in the system of higher theatre education in Ukraine, there is no inclusive education system, which, in turn, encourages further in-depth study of this problem by teachers and cinema and theatre critics.

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**ІНКЛЮЗИВНЕ СЦЕНІЧНЕ
ТА ПЕРФОРМАТИВНЕ МИСТЕЦТВО
У ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ УКРАЇНСЬКОГО
КУЛЬТУРНОГО ФОНДУ**

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Мета статті — аналітично осмислити значення діяльності Українського культурного фонду (УКФ) (2017–2019 роки) для розвитку інклюзивного сценічного та перформативного мистецтва в Україні. Методологія дослідження передбачає узагальнення та аналіз діяльності Українського культурного фонду щодо політики надання грантової підтримки, а також прогнозування тенденцій розвитку вітчизняного інклюзивного сценічного та перформативного мистецтва. Наукова новизна. За основними показниками роботи Фонду досліджено структуру грантової підтримки проєктів, простежено еволюцію діяльності та детально проаналізовано особливості інклюзивних вистав. Висновки. В Україні попри соціально-економічні потрясіння держава сприяє розвитку культурно-мистецьких практик, зокрема інклюзивних. Значне місце у цьому процесі належить Українському культурному фонду, що на конкурсній основі фінансує культурно-мистецькі проєкти різновекторного спрямування. Донорську підтримку Фонду надають іноземні партнери. Вагому частку грантової допомоги за програмою «Інклюзивне мистецтво» у 2019 році отримав сектор «Перформативне та сценічне мистецтво» зі значною кількістю профінансованих вистав. Констатовано низку фактів, зокрема: географічно підтримані УКФ проєкти фактично охоплюють усю територію країни, окрім анексованого Криму та тимчасово окупованих територій Донбасу з деяким домінуванням м. Києва; лівову частку серед отриманих грантів становлять сценічні постановки

самодіяльних колективів; сценічні інклюзивні проекти не обмежуються лише створенням театральних вистав та їхньою публічною демонстрацією, а супроводжуються громадсько-реабілітаційними та просвітницько-популярними заходами. Закцентовано на важливості поки нерозроблених проектів для розв'язання життєвих проблем людей з нанизмом, або карликовістю.

Ключові слова: Український культурний фонд; інклюзивне перформативне та сценічне мистецтво

**ИНКЛЮЗИВНОЕ СЦЕНИЧЕСКОЕ
И ПЕРФОРМАТИВНОЕ ИСКУССТВО
В ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ УКРАИНСКОГО
КУЛЬТУРНОГО ФОНДА**

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Цель статьи — аналитически осмыслить значение деятельности Украинского культурного фонда (УКФ) (2017–2019 годы) для развития инклюзивного сценического и перформативного искусства в Украине. Методология исследования предполагает обобщение и анализ деятельности Украинского культурного фонда о политике предоставления грантовой поддержки, а также прогнозирование тенденций развития отечественного инклюзивного сценического и перформативного искусства. Научная новизна. По основным показателям работы Фонда исследована структура грантовой поддержки проектов, прослежена эволюция деятельности и детально проанализированы особенности инклюзивных представлений. Выводы. В Украине, несмотря на социально-экономические потрясения, государство способствует развитию культурных практик, в частности инклюзивных. Значительное место в этом процессе принадлежит Украинскому культурному фонду, который на конкурсной основе финансирует культурно-художественные проекты разновекторного направления. Донорскую поддержку Фонду предоставляют иностранные партнеры. Весомую долю грантовой помощи по программе «Инклюзивное искусство» в 2019 году получил сектор «Перформативного и сценического искусства» с большим количеством профинансированных представлений. Констатировано ряд фактов, в частности: географически поддержанные УКФ проекты фактически охватывают всю территорию страны, кроме аннексированного Крыма и временно оккупированных территорий Донбасса с некоторым преобладанием г. Киева; львиную долю среди полученных грантов составляют сценические постановки самодеятельных коллективов; сценические инклюзивные проекты не ограничиваются только созданием театральных представлений и их публичной демонстрацией, а сопровождаются общественно-реабилитационными и просветительско-популярными мерами. Акцентировано на важности пока неразработанных проектов для решения жизненных проблем людей с нанизмом, или карликовостью.

Ключевые слова: Украинский культурный фонд; инклюзивное перформативное и сценическое искусство